

A Systematic Review of the Research on Cluster Approach in Teaching Foreign Languages

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Abstract. This research paper aimed at providing a systematic review of the research conducted on the application of the cluster approach in language teaching since the beginning of the 21st century and up to the moment of the research. The articles for the analysis have been selected from seven renowned scientific databases (including EBSCO, Zenodo, Scopus, Science Direct, SAGE, Open AIRE, and Web of Science). The number of total articles identified in the initial research was 32, out of this number, only 7 articles were selected for the review using predefined inclusion criteria. The selected articles have been analyzed and coded into different categories: research design, location, context, level of education, learning outcomes and pedagogical implications. The review analysis showed the major trends and outcomes in the cluster approach topic. It also provided useful information about the application of the cluster approach in language teaching, including teaching foreign languages on the medium and high levels of secondary school education. The study contributes to some unaddressed points identified in the selected articles, and it recommends some points to be considered in the future research on the issue of cluster approach in teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: Systematic review; cluster approach; foreign language; language skills.

Introduction. The theories of English language teaching keep developing to serve the best education for learners and cater to their needs. The history of English language teaching witnessed many attempts to find the most effective approaches for teaching language. Richard and Rodgers (2014) pointed out that language teaching has become a profession on its own in the twentieth century. This profession continues to scout about new issues and the effectiveness of various teaching methods and approaches to overcome those issues.

The Grammar-Translation Method was first introduced to be formalized in the classroom. Nonetheless, it receives criticism because of its bilingual strategy to teaching, while language teaching and learning is spontaneous, and learners can use the target language as a medium of instruction.

The criticism on the Grammar-Translation Method has led to developing the Direct Method as a monolingual approach for language teaching.

During the 1950s, the Audiolingual Method has been introduced to train military personnel to use oral language. This method became popular in schools, but it was criticized because of its focus on repetitive drills and memorization.

Subsequently, the Cognitive Method has emerged, and it mainly focuses on generative grammar and cognitive psychology. This method received much attention among language learners and teachers because it considers learners as active participants regardless of the errors they might commit (Mei, 2018). This method is limited to teaching a language out of the context instead of in-context, thus it has been viewed as a weak teaching approach.

The Situational Teaching Method has been developed and it focuses on teaching and practicing a language in situations. The emergence of this teaching method was seen as a major development in the field of language teaching Gao (2019). However, this method was criticized as it predicts what and how language is used in a specific situation when in fact, language use cannot be predicted (Mwanza, 2020).

As a result, the communicative language teaching method evolved in the 1980s. This method received extra attention at that time because it concentrates on language use, regardless of the situation or context. This method is seen as prescriptive and outdated in some contexts because the decisions and methods of language teaching cannot be prescribed. The teaching environment should be dynamic where teachers are encouraged to operate.

All the developed teaching methods had their strengths and limitations. There was no real and dynamic language teaching method in the classroom setting. This led to the emergence of the cluster teaching approach which is claimed to be the suitable approach for language teaching.

Literature Review. The cluster approach is a teaching style used in teaching a second or a foreign language. This approach combines the principles of various methods and approaches of teaching a language depending on the lesson objectives and individual differences of students (Kushieva, 2019; Adilova, 2022; Allamuratov, 2022; Dushayeva, 2023).

According to Charles (2005), the cluster theory of language teaching has emerged in the 1990s as an additional theory of language teaching. The cluster approach becomes popular because it contributes to achieving the learning objectives without much pressure on both teachers and learners.

The cluster approach helps in having a clearer vision for learners of what they are learning (Vong, 2012). Teaching with this approach includes but is not limited to using multiple tasks, lively learning and high interaction between students and teachers.

Baranova, Martynova and Ereemeeva (2018) emphasized the importance of the cluster approach in teaching. In her point of view, the cluster approach is pluralistic, consistent and entails diverse learning activities that match with learners' needs.

According to Gao (2011), the principles of cluster approach would challenge instructors to ensure that decisions about classroom instruction and activities are based on a holistic and comprehensive understanding of all teaching theories and pedagogies, in terms of the goal and situation of language teaching and learning, learners' needs, the available materials and how language is learned.

Howard (2007) viewed cluster approach as a teaching method that combines all language skills (e.g. listening, speaking, reading and writing) and encompasses some practice in the classroom. He also advises teachers to integrate and take advantage of all other teaching methods and to avoid their disadvantages.

Gabbol (2005) stated that principled cluster approach should not serve methods and methodology themselves, but learners. Thus, it is up to the teachers' discretion to choose procedures and techniques inside the classroom. Each one of the language teaching methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, and there is no concrete or ideal approach in language teaching.

The cluster teaching approach is characterized by keen flexibility since teachers can choose whatever works to achieve learning objectives (Yumimoto, 2020).

It is extremely important to note that the cluster approach is not rigorous, and its features are combined with other teaching methods. Kowney and Segal (2014) attempted to explain the major characteristics and principles of clusterism as follows:

(1) Teachers are free to select various types of teaching techniques in the classroom with reference to the lesson objectives.

(2) Teachers could choose any method or aspect that suits teaching inside the classroom.

(3) Learners will see different teaching aids that make lessons more stimulating and interesting.

(4) Teachers and learners would be in a better situation to overcome difficulties that may arise from the textbook materials.

(5) The cluster approach saves much time and effort in the presentation of language activities.

(6) The cluster approach is subjective since it is constructed by teachers according to the learning context.

In a similar vein, Polilova and Ponomarev (2007) indicated some prominent features of clusterism as follows:

(1) Cluster approach makes teaching more enjoyable and innovative.

(2) It enhances the active interaction between students and teachers.

(3) Caters to the individual needs of learners.

(4) Enhances practical teaching as it facilitates retention and builds self-confidence.

(5) Cluster approach enables instructors to achieve the learning objectives easily.

(6) It is a problem-based approach to teaching languages that solves the problems encountered by the students in class.

(7) Testing is not a separate element but a part of this approach.

(8) Learners would have a clear vision of what they are learning.

(9) This approach includes various tasks such as higher interaction, lively learning, correlative learning and fast results.

(10) Cluster approach connects life experiences of learners to the ideas presented in language learning.

The teacher should carefully select the materials to suit the learning context and make the teaching process more motivating and interesting. Raxmonov and Luxmanov (2020) affirmed that good teachers spend much time in collecting attractive and interesting teaching materials to gladden their teaching. Teachers should not spare a thought in developing materials for the learners. In cluster approach, teachers can use computers, pictures, maps, music, film, radio, newspapers, magazines, textbooks, research articles, chats and realia in their teaching.

Methodology. The data of this study have been collected through searching in electronic journals and databases. The present review adopted certain criteria for articles selection and inclusion. The criteria include the following: (1) The article must be an empirical study. (2) The article has explicitly investigated the cluster approach in language teaching. (3) The article must have been published in conference proceedings or journals between 2000 and 2023. This time frame was specified to review the most recent research of the topic under investigation. (4) The articles must be written in the English or Uzbek languages. (5) The articles must contain an abstract. This is very important to select relevant research manuscripts. (6) The present review concentrates on the use of the cluster approach

in teaching the English language; thus, any article that investigates the use of the cluster approach in teaching other subjects will be excluded.

Results. The systematic review of the cluster approach in language teaching shows some similarities and differences between the selected articles. It is obvious that most of the articles used quasi-experimental and mixed methods as a research design. Other articles used surveys, qualitative, or experimental research designs.

Most of the participants in the selected articles were from secondary schools (21) studies, followed by participants from higher education (19) studies and participants from primary education (7) studies. The selected articles studied the cluster approach in language teaching from different perspectives. However, all the studies come to a consensus that the use of the cluster approach has a positive impact on enhancing the learning of a second or foreign language. The studies emphasized on combining different techniques and activities in the learning process. They viewed the cluster approach as collaborative learning and they all agreed that learning in groups would be beneficial for the students, creating a more enjoyable and motivating environment.

Most of the studies recommend the adoption of the cluster approach due to its importance to avoid boredom in the class and accurately address the learning objectives. These studies recommended engaging teachers in explicit training to adopt the cluster approach successfully. Only two studies recommended shifting to a learner-centered curriculum in which students will be responsible for their learning and teachers' role is limited to guidance and direction.

The current review has explored the research conducted on the cluster approach in language teaching. It was apparent that the studies conducted in South America and Europe have been minimal. Consequently, there is a persistent need to conduct more studies in these regions to get clearer insights into the impact of the cluster approach on language teaching. Most of the reviewed studies have been conducted on students from secondary and tertiary levels. Very few studies have focused on students from the elementary level.

The reviewed studies have mainly focused on the use/impact of the cluster approach on the teaching of the English language in general. However, it is very important to investigate the applications of the cluster approach in the teaching of specific language components such as grammar, reading, writing, listening or speaking. It will be very useful to explore how teachers apply this approach to teach specific language components.

Most of the studies have focused on examining the impact of applying the cluster approach in teaching particular topics and/or lessons. Hence, it would be a very good idea to investigate and observe teachers in a long-time span to check whether or not, teachers are cluster in every lesson. There is also a need to conduct comparative studies between public and private schools in the use and impact of the cluster approach on students' performance.

These comparative studies could also include students' level as a variable when studying the impact of the cluster approach on language teaching. All the aforementioned points could bridge the gaps on this topic and provide more insights and clearer pictures for students, teachers, curriculum and policymakers.

Discussion. We point out that more teaching materials have significantly entered the classroom in the twenty-first century, such as sound, image and movement. We state that teaching can be meaningful in the classroom through the interaction of spoken voice, sound effects, music and pictures. This implicates using a variety of resources appropriate to the learning objectives, and not be limited to speech. Therefore, cluster teachers should be

creative in using materials and objects, for example, teachers can use pictures and movements to teach English verb tenses.

Like any other teaching method, the cluster teaching approach has advantages and disadvantages. The cluster approach is live, motivating, participatory, context-sensitive, learner-centered and includes using a variety of classroom tasks and activities. In addition, the cluster approach is flexible to the needs of the classroom during the lesson, it is correlative and objective since it addresses the learners' needs of diverse backgrounds. The cluster approach is said to have disadvantages that include (1) discouraging teachers to reflect upon their teaching; (2) The adoption of the cluster approach could be unsafe due to the methodological baggage that comes with it. Nonetheless, the cluster approach is more advantageous than disadvantageous; most of the limitations of this approach are justifiable when teachers are poorly prepared for the classroom.

We argue that cluster approach allows teachers to select the materials that work well in their classrooms within their dynamic professional contexts. We also point out that the reason for adopting cluster approach is because it does not rely on a single teaching method or technique. The cluster approach has a broad theoretical basis and has a flexible set of activities. The previous literature on language teaching methods emphasized the importance of investigating the role of cluster approach in language teaching. However, there is a lack of systematic reviews that shed light on studies investigating the use of the cluster approach in language teaching. Consequently, this study aims at reporting the different studies that investigated the use of clusterism as an approach for language teaching. It also aims at studying the different trends of the research done in the last few years.

Conclusion. This review study sheds light on the research on the use of the cluster approach in language teaching which is mainly representative and up to date. This systematic review was very useful to determine the major trends and outcomes of the use of the cluster approach in language teaching. All the selected articles have been coded carefully to detect their research design, location, context, level of education, learning outcomes and pedagogical implications.

The similarities and differences between the selected articles have been synthesized along with the gaps not addressed on this topic. The area of the cluster approach is very rich and worthy to be further investigated. Future studies can be useful to explain in detail the impact of applying the cluster approach on teaching language components. The pedagogical implications of the future studies would enhance the performance of students and bridge the underrepresented language learning.

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